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ASSESSMENT OF THE FACTORS IN CHOOSING THE COLLEGE COURSE OF THE FIRST YEAR'S STUDENTS UNDER THE COLLEGE OF ARTS AND SCIENCES AT CAVITE STATE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

This study aims to assess a first-year student's demographic profile and factors influencing college course selection under CAS, using scientific methodologies, statistical analysis, and survey questionnaires to gather data on previous senior high school courses. The study "Assessment on The Factors in Choosing the College Course of the First-year Students under CAS" aims to understand the factors affecting first-year students in choosing their college course

Keywords: *College course, Frequency distribution, Factors, k to 12 programs, Percentage.*

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INTRODUCTION

Education is an essential issue in one's life. It is the key to success for a person and many possible life opportunities. It is also one of the known answers for the person or a whole country to eliminate poverty and further advance health, technology, peace, and quality of life. Many people believe education is the key to an individual's success, especially Filipinos who place great importance on our education (Al-Shuaibi, 2014).

According to Corazon et al. (2020), some students become anxious and lose interest in pursuing higher education when there is a gap between high school coursework and university courses. On the other hand, for students that are still pursuing their college degree, Ouano et al. (2019) concluded in the study that institutional factors that influence student's college decisions include location, educational facilities, cost, and employment opportunities.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aims to assess the Factors in choosing the college course for a first-year student under the College of Arts and Sciences. Specifically, This study aimed to assess the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Sex by birth, Age, Senior High Strand, and College course and also, to assess the factors in choosing the college course of first-year students under CAS.

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METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative-descriptive survey via questionnaire, of which copies were distributed to the student-respondents. This is to assess the students to the factors that affect their choosing course in their college, the factors such as (i) student-related factors (ii) peer pressure, and (iii) future job opportunities.

This study utilized two-stage Stratified Sampling techniques to select the respondents. Two Two-stage stratified sampling is selecting respondents by separating the population into groups or strata considering the demographic profile of the respondents and the factors in choosing the college course of the first-year students under CAS. The dichotomous scale measures the factors in choosing the college course of first-year students under the College of Arts and Sciences since the focus of this research is to assess the experience of a 1st-year student in choosing their preferred college course.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Demographic Data

The respondents to this study totaled 258 Students from the College of Arts and Science at Cavite State University (20 from Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies, 47 from Journalism, 22 from Political Science, 25 from Applied Math, 43 from Biology, 67 from Psychology, and 34 from Social Works. The demographic information of the respondents is summarized as follows:

CATEGORY	Frequency	PERCENTAGE
SEX		
Male	108	41.6
Female	150	58.13
AGE		
18	46	17.82
19	134	51.93
20	59	22.86
21	19	7.36
STRAND		
STEM	78	30.23
ABM	14	5.42
HUMMS	109	42.24
GAS	50	19.37
OTHERS	7	2.71
COURSE		
Political Science	22	8.52
Applied Mathematics	25	9.69
Psychology	64	25.97
Biology	43	16.67
Journalism	47	18.22
Arts in English Language Studies	20	7.75
Social Works	34	13.18

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B. Statistical Data

The all-inclusive result of the data gathered as illustrated, shows that a significant number of respondents stated that their strand correlated with the course they plan to take on college.

To the Student-Related Factors

I consider my personality to the program that I choose.	218	40
I consider my academic performance to the program that I choose.	222	36
I consider the strand that I took before choosing my program.	219	39
I consider my skills and talent before choosing my program	210	48
I consider the result of my NCAE after choosing my strand and program	118	140

To the Future Job Opportunities

I find that the course I choose is convenient for looking a job in the future.	196	62
I find that my program offers a stability status for the job.	207	51
I find that the availability of the job suits me	217	41
I find favorable for the tenure ship to the job.	171	87
I find that my program offers a good salary on my future job.	196	62

To the Peer Influence

My peer influences me to choose what I like to choose	110	148
My peers encourage me to do things to achieve my goals	145	113
My peers' advice encourages me to learn what I want to choose.	156	102
I prefer to choose what my peer taken for us to be in group.	121	137
I let my peer to choose what I want to choose	65	193

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YES

Figure 4.1: Graph of Factors that answered by Yes

Figure 4.1 shows the percentage of students who said yes to the factors, stating that the Future Job Opportunities Factor is 38.4% equal to the Student Related Factors 38.4 % while the Peer Influence is 23.2 % which is insignificant to the respondents.

Figure 4.2 Graph of Factors that answered by No.

Figure 4.2 shows that the Future Job Opportunities and Student-Related Factors 23.3% answered no, while Peer Influence 53.3% answered no.

NO

Figure 4.1 and 4.2

Data gathered in Figures 4.1 and 4.2 show the factors that affect student-related factors Future job opportunities have more components to the students and the Peer influence is insignificant.

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CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the data that have been gathered and interpreted by the researchers, The factors that greatly affect the students on choosing their college program corresponding to their previous senior high School strand are the students' related factors and future job opportunities since it ranked first among the three listed factors. The students' related factors and future job opportunities got 987 responses from the respondents thus, these factors directly affect the students' decision-making in terms of choosing their college programs. The peer influence has the lowest total with 597 responses and on the other side, the students' related factors and future jobs have the same total of 303 responses and the peer influence has the highest responses with 693 total responses.

This information will give the students awareness and knowledge about the factors that affect the senior students in choosing their college course and also might affect them in choosing their college course.

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